

TRANSLATION ACTIVITIES ON ORAL TRANSLATION

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ANNOTATION

Translation in groups can encourage learners to discuss the meaning and use of language at the deepest possible levels as they work through the process of understanding and then looking for equivalents in another language. Translation is a real-life, natural activity and increasingly necessary in a global environment. It does not consider the role of the L1 as a teaching tool, for example for classroom management, setting up activities, or for explaining new vocabulary. This question has been discussed elsewhere on the Teaching English site. The article starts by looking at what we mean by translation as an activity in the language classroom, and then briefly reviews the history of translation in language learning within the framework of various methodologies. It then considers some of the many objections ELT thinkers and practitioners have had to translation, and some of the possible benefits of its use. It concludes with some observations about how to make translation tasks successful, and some activities.

KEY WORDS: Oral translation, Written translation, translation activities, simultaneous translation,

1.INTRODUCTION

Traditionally considered a challenging activity for our most able linguists, it is high time we made translation more accessible to less able and younger language learners. This could be done by breaking tasks down into word, sentence and text level activities, linked with speaking as well as writing. In this way, translation will enable us to help all language learners build up their vocabulary and improve their

command of key idiomatic structures. The fact that translation is not just a linguistic procedure but is socially constructed and oriented just like language itself, is gradually accepted. Hence, translators are becoming fully aware that training is necessary just as in any other profession if one wants to keep up with global changes. One of the major challenges in translation and interpretation is the inadequate translation quality of texts as well as poor simultaneous and consecutive interpreting during conferences, training, and other important events. However, in the case of written translations, the translator has the chance to intervene, correct, and proofread the text through proofreaders, which is not a touch that can be done during oral interpretation. This does not mean that interpretation has any lower stakes; poor oral interpretation can even result in the failure of an event, e.g. interlocutors may misunderstand each other or convey an inaccurate intellectual or professional

picture of the speakers. Therefore, this paper explores the challenges and solutions of translation, in general, and oral interpretation, in particular.

1.1 Translation is an activity that aims to facilitate the communication process by interpreting the information received in one language (L1) into another language (L2), and vice versa. The basic function of translation is to transmit appropriate meaning of a word or a sentence linguistically semantically and pragmatically. If this complex process is carried out on a professional level, then, it is possible to say that translation has reached its ultimate goal.

Foreign language learners frequently use translation to facilitate language learning and to acquire the new language. Despite the fact that translation has played different roles in various methods of language teaching accommodated for students from different social backgrounds, most educators agree that translation is a powerful tool to help the student more confidently understand foreign words and expressions and express ideas in the target language. Nevertheless, some educators argue against

- Financial Translation
- Legal Translation

Let's take a look at the challenges and requirements for each type of translation.

Literary Translation

As the name suggests, literary translation is the act of translating literary works, such as plays, novels and poems. The main challenge with these types of texts is that you need to translate the meaning while also considering the author's unique literary style.

Stylistic devices are one of the most important characteristics of literary texts. They can be found in everything from rhythm and meter to word choices, imagery and the innate balance of the sentences. Then there are also puns, humor and rhyme to contend with. These all use the source language in a specific way, and often there is no direct equivalence between the source and target languages.

This means that translators often need to get creative so that they can recreate the same effect that the original text had on its readers. Other challenges include nuances, such as cultural sensibilities, connotations and emotions, along with the social, historical and political context of the text. These nuances are especially hard to convey and might also be considered untranslatable.

Every author has a unique literary style which is reflected in their writing, with each sentence and paragraph giving the reader a sense of their personality, beliefs and emotions. Since style is such an integral part of these types of texts, translations should try to emulate the originals. This means that literary translators must master

literary techniques in both languages if they are to produce an ideal version of a foreign masterpiece.

Technical Translation

Technical documents are necessary for companies to comply with local and international standards. In the era of globalisation, technical translation applies to a wide variety of text types including patents, manuals, user guides, tender documents, catalogues, technical drawings and Material Safety Data Sheets (MSDS).

This broad range of text types means that technical translation is needed in almost every industry, from engineering and construction to life sciences and pharmaceuticals. It is this variety of subject domains is that makes technical translation especially challenging, since each comes with its own specialist jargon. Translators also need an in-depth understanding of how technical texts are written, their nature and their legal requirements.

A great technical translator not only knows the technical terminology but also understands specific subject and industry jargon. This allows them to produce a translation that clearly conveys the correct message by making the right word choices.

Administrative Translation

The administrative department oversees the day-to-day workings of a business, and as such, administrative translation plays a crucial role in management. This covers a broad scope of documents relating to business processes and daily activities, including contracts, newsletters, invoices and letters.

Organisations usually need this type of translation when looking to establish or maintain their global presence. It allows them to break down language barriers within the global economy, increasing their opportunities to grow and embracing a multi-cultural workforce. This ensures that business partners, investors and employees are all on the same page, creating clear channels of communication for a better functioning business.

Financial Translation

Financial translation is crucial in today's global marketplace and holds great importance for banks, insurance companies and other financial institutions. It helps them expand access to their services and build trust among customers while making sure they comply with international regulations.

As financial companies move into developing markets, the demand for high-quality financial translation increases. From annual and tax reports to profit and loss statements and company accounts, this sector involves a range of documents requiring versatile language specialists with industry-specific skills.

These financial documents are highly regulated, and as such, translators must be familiar with local laws and regulations. That way, they can understand the differences between the source and target documents, ensuring that the target text complies with target market rules.

The financial industry also goes hand in hand with technology and innovation, meaning that new financial instruments and innovative concepts come to market almost every day. As such, many new buzzwords are being added to an already overwhelming glossary of specific terms and phrases. This means that translators

need to stay on top of industry developments, constantly learning new terms in both their native and secondary languages.

Legal Translation

Legal translation is one of the more complicated types of professional translation and refers to the translation of any legal documents. Examples include contracts, company or government proposals, court transcripts, service-level agreements (SLAs), laws, witness statements, notarised documents and many more.

As you expand into new international markets, you need to ensure that your legal documents are understood, respected and legally binding for all audiences. As such, the translator must understand the political, legal and socio-cultural context of a legal text. This will allow them to translate it in a way that anyone from different cultural, political and social backgrounds can readily understand.

Legal documents must be translated accurately while also following the writing norms of the target language. Only a translation agency that understands both the source and target cultures can produce a good legal translation. However, the slightest miswording can have disastrous consequences. As such, even translation specialists will seek professional legal help to make certain that the target text offers the same legal protection as the original.

e function

1.2 The simultaneous translation is an interpreting that is performed during the speech, at the same time with the reproduction of the text in the original language. The parallel dubbing of information in several languages complicates the perception. Therefore, the special techniques are used for the simultaneous translation. Simultaneous interpreting is indispensable at official events with a large number of

with a number of tasks drawing on easy-to-use web tools. The book also considers the relationship between translation and intercultural understanding.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In recent years, however, theorists and researchers working in the Cognitive paradigm have been re-assessing the role of the L1 and translation as a means to support and enhance L2 acquisition. Numerous studies seem to indicate that translation does indeed provide numerous cognitive advantages in instructed L2 settings over 100% Target Language.

Consequently, as often happens in modern language education, the pendulum has swung back again and Modern Language Exam now includes a mandatory translation module.

The most valuable advantage of translation pertains, in my opinion, to the cognitive comparison between the L2 and the L1 it promotes, which often results in noticing the gap between the two languages, thereby potentially preempting/correcting L1 negative transfer or, conversely, providing confirmation for L1 positive transfer. As it is obvious from the previous point, translation tasks are fully integrated in the instructional sequence at hand. They are not simply intended to practise translation skills; they are a means to reinforce the chunks and patterns at hand. Translation tasks for use at lower levels of proficiency should be designed in a way that minimizes cognitive overload. This means that with average ability students I never place more than one challenging item per sentence. For instance, if I know my students struggle with the perfect tense of verbs requiring *Etre* as an auxiliary I will not include in that sentence a lexical item or morphological or syntactic structure that is likely to cause divided attention.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion translation is process of converting words or text from one language into another language, but it is not always as simple or literal as it seems. Word for word translation is certainly necessary for certain tasks that require complete accuracy. Technical translation is good example. But not all translation tasks require creativity on the part of translator. A translator must engage in a process of negotiation between two cultures, two languages and sometimes two entirely different worldviews. What works in one context might not be appropriate or acceptable in another. It's the translators job to navigate how to use different words to achieve the same meaning. That's where a level of creativity comes in.

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